

Use of Cobalt Molybdate in the Catalytic Vapour Phase Oxidation of Toluene

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The catalytic activity of unsupported and silica, alumina supported Cobalt molybdate was investigated in the vapour phase oxidation of toluene to produce benzaldehyde and benzoic acid. Results on some catalysts which showed an appreciable effect are reported. The temperature, concentration of catalyst and space velocities were varied over a wide range with each catalyst. The best results were obtained with cobalt molybdate, 80% supported on silica gel at a temperature of 500°, space velocity 9730 ± 20 litre hour⁻¹ litre⁻¹, air/hydrocarbon ratio 610. The yield of benzaldehyde on the basis of toluene reacted is 63.23% per pass and conversion to benzaldehyde is 8.51%.

THE oxidation of aromatic compounds for the production of partially oxygenated derivatives has become of great industrial importance. Benzaldehyde finds wide uses in chemical industry. The increasing demand for pure benzaldehyde has stimulated interest in its production by the direct oxidation of toluene vapours in presence of suitable catalysts. Most of the active catalyst systems used to date are covered by patents. In general the catalysts used consist of vanadium and/or molybdenum oxides and a third component, such as TiO₂, CuO and P₂O₅ and they may be either supported or unsupported.

Volynkin^{1,2} studied the oxidation of toluene to benzaldehyde over a number of solids, partially reduced catalysts and in presence of catalysts occurring in molten metals. The maximum yield of benzaldehyde reported is 50% (based on the toluene reacted) at 670°, but much higher values have been claimed in the patent literature by Ray *et al.*³. If V₂O₅, V₂O₅-MoO₃ and MoO₃-P₂O₅ are used as catalyst, the main oxidation products of toluene are benzaldehyde, benzoic acid with traces of maleic acid CO and CO₂^{4,5}. Mamoru and Sadio⁶ have reported the enhanced activity of MoO₃-P₂O₅ catalyst by the addition of Bi₂O₃.

Recently Sharma and Bhattacharyya⁷ have reported the oxidation products of toluene over molten mixed oxides (in fused state).

The present investigation describes our studies on the heterogeneous vapour phase catalytic oxidation of toluene vapours over supported and unsupported cobalt molybdate catalysts.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either BDH, AnalaR quality or E. Merck 'GR' reagents. Toluene was distilled before it was used.

Catalyst(I), 20% supported cobalt molybdate catalyst was prepared when 22.1 gm sodium molybdate dissolved in hot water was added to known amount of silica gel or alumina gel, containing 80 gm SiO₂ or Al₂O₃ in water and to this 26.58 gm cobalt nitrate dissolved in water was added with constant stirring. The resulting mixture was evaporated on water bath and the solid (CoMoO₄/support 1:4) was dried. This is finally heated in a furnace at about 550° and sieved to get the -18 +24 Tyler mesh size fraction.

The flow diagram of the apparatus used is shown in Fig. 1. The reactor (R) was made of a pyrex glass tube of internal dia 3 cm and 70 cm long. Another glass tube of 1 cm bore kept concentric with the reactor was used for inserting the thermocouple. Reactor was connected to another glass tube which functions as preheater zone (P.H.). The catalyst was packed in the reactor between two plugs of

Fig. 1. Apparatus used for the Oxidation of Toluene in a fixed bed.

A, A₁, A₂ Bubblers; F, Flowmeter; S₁-S₅, Stop-Cocks; A₁, Air Dryer; A₄, Trap; B; Toluene Bubbler; P.H., Preheater; V₁, V₂ Variable Transformers; F=Furnace, R, Reactor, T₁-T₄, Product Receiver; C₁-C₂, Condenser; T₅, Carbondioxide Trap; T₆=Aldehyde Trap; G, Stack Gases.

purified glass-wool. The reactor and preheater zones were heated by two separate tubular heaters controlled by variable transformers (V_1 & V_2). The temperature of the catalyst bed was measured with a calibrated chromel-alumel thermocouple. After each experiment, the proper packing of the catalyst in the catalyst zone was checked so as to ensure proper gas solid contact during the run.

The catalyst was charged in the reactor. Purified air was bubbled through a toluene bubbler, after passing through a flow meter. Toluene bubbler was heated to 60°, 70° and 100°. The air/toluene mixture thus required was heated to 400° before it was introduced in the reactor.

The reaction products were collected in an air condenser, water condenser and finally through an ice cold condenser. To stop benzaldehyde vapours from escaping along with the air stream the affluent gases were passed through a bubbler containing 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine solution. Carbon dioxide produced in the reaction was absorbed by 250 ml of standard solution of potassium hydroxide (5%), kept in three bubblers. The quantitative estimation of the products was done by the method similar to one suggested by Kumar, Bhat and Kuloor⁸. The specific surface area of the catalyst supports was determined by BET method using nitrogen gas as adsorbent.

Parameters studied :

Runs were carried out with the above catalysts at the following conditions :

- (1) Reaction temperature : 350 to 550°

- (2) Air-toluene ratio : 350 to 696
- (3) Space velocity : 5860 to 14081 ± 1 litre/hr/litre

Definitions :

During the consideration of the results and discussions the various terms used are defined as follows :

- (1) Air/Toluene ratio = $\frac{\text{Volume of the air in the reaction mixture}}{\text{Volume of the toluene passed}}$
- (2) Space Velocity = $\frac{\text{Volume of the gas mixture (dry air and toluene vapour) at N. T. P. passing per hour per volume of the catalyst litre hr}^{-1} \text{ litre}^{-1}}$
- (3) Conversion % (to a particular product) = $\frac{\text{Grams toluene converted to a particular product}}{\text{Grams toluene passed}} \times 100$
- (4) Yield of Benzaldehyde. = $\frac{\text{Toluene Converted to benzaldehyde}}{\text{Toluene converted to partial and complete oxygenated product}} \times 100$

All temperatures are the temperatures of the catalyst zone.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained with various catalysts are given in Tables 1 to 4, and representative examples have been plotted from these data. The discussion herewith describes the results obtained with catalyst IV, Table 1 (CoMoO_4 80% on SiO_2) in the following manner.

TABLE 1—ACTIVITY DATA FOR VARIOUS CATALYSTS
EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AT CONSTANT SPACE VELOCITY 9730 ± 20 lit hr⁻¹ litre⁻¹
APPARENT VOLUME OF THE CATALYST=30 c.c.

Catalyst	Catalyst composition CoMoO_4 : SiO_2	Temperature °C	Air/ Toluene ratio	Specific surface area of the cata- lyst support m ² /gm	Conversion %				Total conver- sion %	% Yield of BzH
					BzH	BzA	M.A.	CO ₂		
I	20 : 80	350	610	86.23	3.87	0.96	0.44	1.91	7.18	53.69
		400	602	88.34	4.98	0.88	1.10	2.14	9.10	54.72
		500	602	98.13	6.23	1.08	1.53	2.01	10.85	57.43
		550	610	97.01	4.90	1.14	1.16	2.17	9.97	52.65
II	40 : 60	350	610	86.23	4.41	0.31	0.48	1.63	6.81	65.16
		400	602	88.34	5.61	1.06	1.37	1.76	9.78	57.79
		500	602	98.13	6.98	1.27	1.82	2.15	12.21	57.79
		550	610	97.01	5.51	1.27	1.41	1.78	9.97	55.86
III	60 : 40	350	602	86.23	4.69	0.89	0.64	1.30	7.52	62.10
		400	602	88.34	4.99	0.98	0.28	1.63	7.88	57.92
		500	610	98.13	7.31	1.88	2.00	1.61	12.30	59.45
		550	602	97.01	6.20	1.46	1.65	1.63	10.94	56.74
IV	80 : 20	350	610	86.23	5.80	1.17	1.15	1.45	9.57	60.53
		400	602	88.34	8.46	1.15	1.15	1.75	12.51	66.35
		500	610	98.13	8.51	1.68	1.75	1.58	13.52	63.23
		550	610	97.01	7.71	1.43	1.83	1.60	12.57	61.71
V	100 : 00	350	602	—	3.15	0.41	0.28	2.11	5.95	53.78
		400	602	—	4.15	0.63	0.93	2.24	7.96	52.91
		500	602	—	5.28	0.81	1.35	2.34	9.78	54.30
		550	602	—	4.09	0.84	1.02	2.24	8.19	50.09

BzH=benzaldehyde ; BzA=benzoic acid ; M.A.=maleic acid.

TABLE 2—ACTIVITY DATA FOR VARIOUS CATALYSTS
EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AT CONSTANT SPACE VELOCITY, 9730 ± 20 lit hr⁻¹ litre⁻¹
APPARENT VOLUME OF THE CATALYST=30 c.c.

Catalyst	Catalyst composition CoMoO ₄ : Al ₂ O ₃	Temperature °C	Air/ Toluene ratio	Specific surface area of the cata- lyst support m ² /gm	Conversion %				Total conver- sion %	% Yield of BzH
					BzH	BzA	M.A.	CO ₂		
VI	20 : 80	350	602	87.80	2.16	1.00	0.53	3.06	6.75	32.22
		400	610	99.54	3.41	2.05	1.16	3.11	7.73	35.00
		500	610	96.87	3.49	2.22	1.27	3.49	8.47	33.12
		550	610	96.77	2.26	1.41	0.80	3.11	7.58	30.34
VII	40 : 60	350	602	87.80	2.99	1.38	0.77	3.45	8.59	34.80
		400	610	99.54	3.19	1.48	0.89	3.86	9.42	33.90
		500	602	96.87	3.03	1.32	0.78	4.14	9.27	32.70
		550	610	96.77	3.30	1.38	0.84	4.21	9.63	32.34
VIII	60 : 40	350	610	87.80	3.91	1.61	0.77	4.20	10.49	37.25
		400	602	99.54	4.37	1.61	0.92	4.74	11.64	37.53
		500	602	96.87	3.94	1.48	0.90	5.02	11.34	34.81
		550	610	96.77	4.75	1.53	0.92	3.54	10.74	44.19
IX	80 : 20	350	602	87.80	4.01	1.67	0.83	4.45	10.97	36.66
		400	610	99.54	4.37	1.62	0.94	5.60	12.54	34.68
		500	610	96.87	4.32	2.36	1.28	5.60	13.57	31.83
		550	610	96.77	5.12	1.94	1.19	4.81	13.06	39.47
X	100 : 00	350	602	—	3.15	0.41	0.28	2.11	5.95	53.78
		400	602	—	4.15	0.63	0.93	2.24	7.96	52.91
		500	602	—	5.28	0.81	1.36	2.34	9.78	54.30
		550	602	—	4.09	0.84	1.02	2.24	8.19	50.09

BzH=benzaldehyde ; BzA=benzoic acid ; M.A.=maleic acid.

TABLE 3—ACTIVITY DATA FOR VARIOUS CATALYSTS
EFFECT OF SPACE VELOCITY AT CONSTANT TEMPERATURE 500°C, APPARENT VOLUME OF THE CATALYST=30 c.c.
SPECIFIC SURFACE AREA OF THE CATALYST SUPPORT=98.13 m²/gm

Catalyst	Catalyst composition CoMoO ₄ : SiO ₂	Space velocity litre hour ⁻¹ litre ⁻¹	Air/Toluene ratio	Conversion %				Total conversion %	% Yield of BzH
				BzH	BzA	M.A.	CO ₂		
I	20 : 80	5890	350	4.79	0.66	0.94	1.95	8.28	57.34
		9749	602	6.23	1.08	1.53	2.01	10.85	57.43
		14034	696	6.03	0.75	1.09	1.66	9.51	65.05
II	40 : 60	5890	350	5.25	0.59	1.15	1.60	8.89	59.15
		9749	602	6.98	1.27	1.82	2.15	12.21	57.79
		14034	696	6.65	0.91	1.31	1.53	10.47	64.25
III	60 : 40	5860	352	5.51	0.98	1.29	1.47	9.25	59.84
		9711	610	7.31	1.38	2.00	1.61	12.30	59.45
		14034	696	6.96	1.28	1.45	1.37	11.06	63.14
IV	80 : 20	5860	352	6.14	1.31	1.43	1.32	10.20	60.62
		9711	610	8.51	1.68	1.75	1.58	13.52	63.23
		14081	692	5.62	1.35	2.02	1.36	10.69	66.44
V	100 : 00	5890	350	4.03	0.46	0.80	3.03	8.32	56.73
		9749	602	5.28	0.81	1.35	2.34	9.78	54.30
		14034	696	5.23	0.53	0.94	2.04	8.74	65.29

BzH=benzaldehyde ; BzA=benzoic acid ; M.A.=maleic acid.

TABLE 4—ACTIVITY DATA FOR VARIOUS CATALYSTS
 EFFECT OF SPACE VELOCITY AT CONSTANT TEMPERATURE 500°C, APPARENT VOLUME OF THE CATALYST=30 c.c.
 SPECIFIC SURFACE AREA OF THE CATALYST SUPPORT=96.87 m²/gm

Catalyst	Catalyst composition CoMoO ₄ : Al ₂ O ₃ litre ⁻¹	Space velocity litre hr ⁻¹	Air/Toluene ratio	Conversion%				Total conversion %	% Yield of BzH
				BzH	BzA	M.A.	CO ₂		
VI	20 : 80	5890	350	2.11	1.26	0.72	2.01	6.10	34.92
		9711	610	3.49	2.22	1.27	3.49	8.47	33.12
		14034	630	2.94	2.08	1.00	3.61	9.63	30.23
VII	40 : 60	5890	350	3.70	1.60	0.96	3.47	9.73	38.16
		9749	602	3.03	1.32	0.74	4.14	9.27	32.70
		14081	692	3.01	1.28	0.77	4.16	9.22	32.69
VIII	60 : 40	5890	350	4.85	1.85	0.96	4.32	11.98	40.52
		9749	602	3.94	1.48	0.90	5.02	11.34	34.81
		14081	692	4.00	1.80	0.80	3.87	10.07	39.76
IX	80 : 20	5890	350	5.26	1.89	1.02	4.81	12.99	40.76
		9711	610	4.32	2.36	1.28	5.60	13.57	31.83
		14081	692	4.27	0.18	1.09	4.44	9.99	37.62
X	100 : 00	5890	350	4.03	0.46	0.80	3.03	8.32	56.73
		9749	602	5.28	0.81	1.35	2.34	9.78	54.30
		14034	696	5.23	0.53	0.94	2.04	8.74	65.29

BzH = benzaldehyde ; BzA = benzoic acid ; M.A. = maleic acid.

Effect of Cobalt Molybdate Concentration :

It is seen from the Fig. 2 that the activity of cobalt molybdate, unsupported, varied with change in its concentration supported on silica gel. The data show that under almost identical conditions maximum conversion of 8.51% yield 63.23% of benzaldehyde was obtained when the ratio of cobalt molybdate silica was 80 : 20, while with the catalyst supported on alumina the maximum conversion to benzaldehyde is 5.26%, Table 3. Probably this composition corresponds to maximum electron work

Fig. 2. Effect of catalyst composition (CoMoO₄ : SiO₂ ratio) on the conversion per cent. Space velocity, 9711—9749 litre hr⁻¹ litre⁻¹, temperature 500° ± 5, Air/Toluene ratio, 602—610.

function of the system studied. Margolis *et al.*⁹ reported that for the oxidation of propene to acrolein by bismuth oxide-molybdenum oxide catalysts the electron work function and activity passes through a maximum with increasing atomic percentage of bismuth in the Bi₂O₃.MoO₃ system.

Effect of Temperature :

The influence of temperature on the conversion is shown in Fig. 3. The optimum temperature obtained in the reaction was 500°. A rise in temperature beyond the optimum value favoured the formation of carbon dioxide and the yield of the

Fig. 3. Effect of temperature on the conversion to various products with catalyst IV (CoMoO₄ 80% on SiO₂). Space velocity 9730 ± 20 litre hr⁻¹ litre⁻¹, Air/Toluene ratio 605 ± 5.

benzaldehyde declined considerably. The efficiency and activity of the catalyst IV was found to be quite sensitive to temperature.

Effect of Space Velocity :

The effect of space velocity on the selectivity and hence activity of the catalyst IV is shown in Fig. 4. The value of space velocity 9711 litre hour⁻¹ litre⁻¹ was found to be optimum. Any increase in space velocity beyond the optimum value lowered the yield of the benzaldehyde. The lowering of per cent conversion and hence yield of the benzaldehyde with increasing space velocity beyond the optimum may be due to the considerable decrease in the contact time.

Fig. 4. Effect of space velocity on the conversion to various products in the presence of catalyst IV (CoMoO⁴: 80% on SiO₂), temperature 500 ± 5°, Air/Toluene 650 ± 40.

The main products of toluene oxidation are benzaldehyde, benzoic acid, maleic acid and carbon dioxide. Bone¹⁰ has reported the formation of benzyl alcohol in the oxidation of toluene, but as such it has not yet been isolated. The possibility for the absence of benzyl alcohol in the products of toluene oxidation is that it might have been consumed by some reactions with toluene which went much faster than its total oxidation or its partial oxidation to benzaldehyde. Some reliable evidence regarding this possibility is available in the homogeneous gas phase oxidation of toluene¹¹.

The reaction initiated through a hydroperoxide¹² which is probably the first intermediate formed in the oxidation of toluene, seems to be

more feasible particularly in the presence of active catalyst and is given below

This intermediate is not very stable because of the availability of orthoelectron to hydroperoxydyl OH and according to suggested mechanism¹³, (1), peroxy compounds can decompose in two fashions, one of which leads to the formation of alcohol.

In the presence of benzaldehyde, the possibility of C₆H₅CH₂OOH radical to undergo reaction II would be high

In the present case also we could not isolate the benzyl alcohol hence the probable reaction may follow the path II as suggested.

Parks and Katz¹⁴ have studied the heterogeneous vapour phase oxidation of toluene and found the exothermic nature of the reaction. The maximum increase in the catalyst temperature was recorded to be 50°. In our present case we have observed that the heat generated during the reaction would not be enough to raise the temperature of the catalyst bed by more than 20°.

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